

Pre-Emptive Conflict Detection Architecture for O-RAN Service Management and Orchestration

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Abstract— The evolution of telecommunications networks from closed to open architectures has led to the development of the Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) standard. O-RAN's Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) typically contains multiple autonomic management agents that simultaneously make configuration changes to optimize aspects of the network. Dealing with competing and conflicting configuration changes from these autonomic management agents remains a major issue. This paper proposes an extension to the O-RAN SMO architecture to incorporate a component that can predict when configuration changes are likely to degrade network performance. The purpose of this approach is to safeguard the actions taken by the management agents against unintended effects. The approach involves the use of two levels of clustering based on cell similarity and cell configuration. The results consist of predictions of network performance degradation based on statistical correlation with network performance.

Keywords— *conflict detection, artificial intelligence, machine learning, telecommunications*

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of open architectures for telecommunications management such as O-RAN where network optimization is carried out by independent autonomous agents has increased the flexibility and adaptability of these systems. The issue of conflict between the actions of multiple autonomous agents each operating with competing goals and within a specific scope is a major issue that has not yet been resolved.

Autonomic network control enables management applications to make real-time reconfigurations to the network without user intervention.

When an autonomic management agent initiates a change to a configuration parameter with the goal of improving a target metric, a key rationale in this decision is a comparison with other elements in the network that are performing more optimally.

A decision can be made by an autonomic management agent to set a configuration parameter to a value used on another element in the network that is yielding better results. This decision is only appropriate if the element being used for comparison is meaningfully similar to the element being re-configured. In such a scenario it must be considered how the configuration of a particular network element is appropriate to its operating conditions. It must also consider

whether configuration changes that might optimize one performance metric could negatively impact another performance metric. In some cases, these 'trade-off' effects are predictable from domain knowledge of the Radio Access Network (RAN) and could be predicted from a knowledge of the association of each configuration parameter with specific functions of the network but in a highly complex system, it is important to consider that some interdependencies between network element configuration and operating efficiency that are not easily understandable or explainable might exist. These interdependencies may be sufficiently convoluted that observation of their effects is a more feasible way to detect them than a model of the behaviors that caused them.

The purpose of the architectural extension to the O-RAN SMO [1] described in this paper is to safeguard the actions taken by the autonomic management agents against unintended effects. The actions can be pre-emptively analyzed to determine if they are likely to cause degradation of network performance on indicators that are outside the scope of the agent that is attempting to take these actions. The specific goal of this architectural extension is to provide feedback to the autonomic management agents about the predicted effects of a configuration change across a broader range of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) than are within the scope of the individual agent.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The pre-emptive conflict detection architecture presented in this paper is based on the O-RAN standard. O-RAN deployments are interoperable across different vendors because they are based on disaggregated, software-based and virtualized components, connected through well-defined and open interfaces. Along with the advantages the flexibility and heterogeneity that this paradigm enables it also brings about the possibility of conflicts between the goals and actions of competing components.

Addressing the problem of conflict between autonomous agents involved in the reconfiguration of a telecommunication network is currently an important challenge in telecommunications management. Research in the areas of O-RAN, SMO, RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC) and conflict detection was conducted in order to better understand the problem domain.

A. O-RAN

A key feature of O-RAN is the deployment of artificial intelligence models embedded in the RIC to provide effective management of the RAN node.

Globally members and contributors of the O-RAN Alliance have committed to evolving radio access networks. The alliance envisions future RANs being built on a foundation of components that fully embrace O-RAN's core principles of intelligence and openness including virtualized network elements, white-box hardware and standardized interfaces. [2]

In "Deep Learning for B5G Open Radio Access Network: Evolution, Survey, Case Studies, and Challenges,"[3] Brik, Boutiba and Ksentini, state that O-RAN is a major paradigm shift in the RAN architecture and discuss its aims to lead the industry towards open, software-driven, virtual, and AI-enabled RANs. Specifically, they mention that the basic idea of O-RAN is to disaggregate the main functions of traditional RAN, implement them as software components i.e., Virtual Network Functions (VNF), and connect them using open and standardized interfaces.

In [4] the authors assess the open interfaces and interoperability aspects of the O-RAN architecture and leverage these features to propose a testing tool for operations and maintenance interfaces of 5G O-RAN base stations.

B. SMO and RAN Intelligent Controller

A key element of the O-RAN architecture is the SMO framework. This component is in charge of handling all orchestration, management, and automation procedures to monitor and control RAN components. Primarily, the SMO hosts the non-real-time RAN Intelligent Controller (non-RT RIC) and provides a set of interfaces that support data collection functionality as well as the interaction between the different network components. This facilitates AI/ML based network monitoring and control. [5]

The RIC provides a centralized abstraction of the network and is a new architectural component that allows operators to implement and deploy custom control plane functions. RAN optimization is facilitated in the RIC through closed-control loops (i.e., autonomous action and feedback loops between RAN components and their controllers). The vision of O-RAN is of separate loops operating at different timescales that range from millisecond (e.g., for transmission strategy real-time control) to multiple seconds (e.g., for network slicing and traffic forecasting). There are two implementations of the RIC in the O-RAN architecture, non-real time (Non-RT) and near-real time (Near-RT). The Non-RT RIC performs operations with a time granularity higher than 1 second, such as training of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) models. The applications hosted at the Non-RT RIC are called rApps. The near-real-time RIC handles procedures at timescales above 10 milliseconds, hosts applications (xApps) that communicate with the telecommunications software through standardized open interfaces, within intelligence in the RAN implemented through data-driven control loops [6].

C. Conflict Detection

In [7] O-RAN WG3 defines conflict mitigation in the context of Near-RT RIC as addressing conflicting interactions between different applications running in the RIC. These definitions are also applicable to the Non-RT RIC although not addressed in the same detail in the current documentation. An application will typically change one or more parameters with the objective of optimizing a specific metric. Conflict mitigation is necessary because xApps objectives may be chosen/configured such that they result in conflicting actions. O-RAN WG3 also defines three different types of conflicts between competing xApps which must be detected. The three categories of conflict are direct, indirect and implicit.

Direct Conflicts: The conflicts can be observed directly and occur when multiple xApps request different settings for the same configuration of one or more parameters of a control target.

Indirect Conflicts: The conflicts cannot be observed directly, nevertheless, some dependence among the parameters and resources involved can be observed. Even though indirect conflicts will not result in conflicting parameter settings, there may be uncontrollable or inadvertent system impacts. For example antenna tilts and measurement offsets are different control points, but they both impact the handover boundary.

Implicit Conflicts: The conflicts cannot be observed directly and the dependencies between competing RIC applications are not obvious. Where different components attempt to optimize different metrics and configure different parameters there still may be implicit, unwanted, and possibly adversary side effects on one of the metrics optimized by another xApp. For example protecting throughput metrics for Guaranteed Bitrate (GBR) users may degrade non-GBR metrics or even cell throughput.

A conflict mitigation framework built into the existing O-RAN architecture is defined by the authors of [8] which enables the Conflict Mitigation component in O-RAN's Near RT RIC to detect and resolve conflicts of all the types defined in the O-RAN Alliance's technical specifications. This framework uses preparatory steps of assigning configuration parameters to parameter groups known to influence the same area of RAN operations.

[9] proposes a solution that aims to mitigate the conflicts between xApps in O-RAN's Near-RT RIC. Specifically, a team learning algorithm which increases cooperation between xApps to enhance the performance of the network. It compares the team learning approach with independent deep Q-learning where network functions individually optimize resources. The study shows that team learning has better network performance under various traffic and user mobility conditions which is demonstrated through simulations.

III. TECHNOLOGY OVERVIEW

This paper presents a solution for pre-emptively detecting potential conflicts between the actions of Non-RT RIC components (rApps) based on a comparison of Key Performance Indicator (KPI) values in similarly performing cells in the telecommunications network. The method involves clustering techniques together with an evaluation of the similarity of time series metrics between the cells.

A. Key Performance Indicators

KPIs are used to measure the performance of a telecommunications network. They are monitored time series of metrics [10]. Categories of KPI include accessibility, retainability, integrity, mobility, and availability. Optimizing a network is a process which involves monitoring the KPI value as a proxy indicator of aspects of the network's performance in each of the categories.

The KPIs used in this paper are based on the latest ETSI/3GPP EUTRAN KPI definitions in [11] and include a variety of measurements across the different KPI categories. An example of a KPI used in this investigation is Random Access Success Rate which describes how often the handshaking procedure on the Random-Access Channel (RACH) is successful. This KPI is defined in technical standards produced by ETSI [12] as follows:

$$\text{Random Access Success Rate [\%]} = 100 * \frac{\text{RACH_Msg3_Received}}{\text{RACH_Msg2_Sent}} (1)$$

and is calculated based on cell level performance counters.

B. Clustering

Cluster analysis is widely used in many fields such as pattern recognition, machine learning, data mining. Clustering is an important research tool attached to unsupervised learning [13]

Clustering is the process of dividing the population into several clusters such that data points in the same groups are more alike to other data points in the same group than those in other groups. The main aim of the clustering technique is to set apart groups with similar features and assign them into clusters using the unsupervised learning process [14]

Clustering is used in the proposed conflict detection component to partition each RAN cell in the input data into category depending on the value of a specific configuration parameter.

C. Time Series Data Mining and Similarity Measurement

Since time series data exists widely across a wide variety of industries, an increasing number of fields use related technologies in Time Series Data Mining (TSDM) for decision support and data analysis. Many different methods of similarity measurement are applied to time series data.

In [15] the authors recognize time series data similarity measurement as a research hotspot and propose a dynamic time-warping algorithm with adaptive segmentation to determine similarities in time series spacecraft telemetry data.

The issue of efficiency of time series similarity research is identified as an obstacle to development of TSDM algorithms in [16]. In this paper the authors propose a time series search algorithm based on dynamic time bending and apply it to hydrological data.

The authors of [17] survey the application of distance and similarity measures to time series data. This study is a comparative analysis which describes Pearson correlation as the 'defacto', 'most widely adopted' and 'most used' proximity measure when dealing with time series data sets.

The similarity measurements underlying the conflict detection component proposed in this paper are described in [18] and are based on a Pearson correlation between a large number of time-series data sets. These data represent various aspects of the operating conditions of cells in the telecommunications network which are measured at fifteen-minute intervals.

IV. TECHNICAL ARCHITECTURE

A. Introduction

Constant optimization of the network is the purpose of a closed-loop control function such as those provided by rApps in the O-RAN architecture. It may result in a change in network behavior which can also be measured in terms of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

The optimization changes may result in KPI degradation. To protect the network performance there should be a mechanism to predict whether the optimization change is likely to result in any degradation in KPIs based on analysis of the dynamic and static state of the running network in the context of its KPIs.

This solution proposes a method for analyzing the available data from the running network in order to predict whether a proposed reconfiguration is likely to negatively impact KPIs in the system.

B. System Overview

The system consists of a component to be deployed in the Non-Real Time RAN Intelligent Controller (Non-RT RIC) of the O-RAN architecture, which provides feedback to the rApps in the Non-RT RIC which are optimizing the network based on individual target KPIs, on each configuration change that they propose.

The conflict detection component accesses data from the PM collections in the RAN to build and maintain a model of the patterns for key metrics which define the dynamic characteristics of each cell in the managed network.

The conflict detection component also accesses current configuration parameter data which details the configuration of each cell so that cells can be judged to be meaningfully similar based on both usage and configuration.

The method proposed does not require detailed modeling of the configuration to map configuration parameters to network functions and deals with each type of conflict defined by O-RAN [I.I.C] generically. This is an alternative approach to the framework described in [8] where the framework’s ability to detect indirect conflicts is based on the creation of groups of parameters known to influence the same area of RAN operations.

C. Implementation

When a reconfiguration change is proposed by an autonomic/closed-loop control agent the proposed reconfiguration/optimization change is fed through the conflict detection component prior to being implemented in the network.

To develop and test the technique for conflict detection a simple architecture was implemented. This architecture consisted of simulated rApps which generated configuration parameter change proposals and a conflict detection rApp that analyzed each of these proposals to predict if it would be likely to cause KPI degradation. To support this analysis the conflict detection rApp consumed performance, configuration and KPI data stored by a segment of a telecommunications network consisting of ~800 cells.

Each of the functions that made up the conflict detection rApp were created using the Python programming language and were deployed in a Jupyter notebook environment for ease of development.

The cells in the network are clustered into 3 groups, one where the configuration parameter, for example the Physical Downlink Control Channel (PDCCH) maximum block error rate, is set to the original value before the proposed reconfiguration and one where the configuration parameter is set to the proposed new value and one in which the configuration parameter is set to a value different from both the original and the new value, only the first two groups are considered as shown in Fig 1.

Fig 1 - Clustering by configuration parameter value

For each group, the most similar cells to the one being reconfigured are calculated based on:

The similarity of their dynamic characteristics, i.e., the correlation of the time series for performance counters

which indicate traffic and usage patterns including throughput volume, physical resource block usage, carrier aggregation metrics, modulation scheme related counters, etc.

The similarity of the remaining set of configuration parameters excluding the proposed reconfiguration parameter under consideration was also calculated. This measurement also contributed to the overall similarity score for each pair of cells in the network segment.

The two sets are analyzed for each KPI being measured by the network. If the proposed new configuration parameter is associated with KPI measurements that are worse than the KPI measurements associated with the existing configuration parameter then the reconfiguration proposal is answered with a message detailing the KPIs likely to be degraded by making this change.

This mechanism, within the Non-RT RIC in the O-RAN architecture, is illustrated in Fig 2.

Fig 2 - Conflict Detection mechanism in O-RAN framework

V. RESULTS

A. Visual Representation of Prediction of KPI Degradation

The results illustrate that applying this method it was possible to identify if potential changes to configuration parameters would be likely to cause KPI degradation. These predictions are based on the statistical correlation between KPI values in cells with a similar operating environment.

In Fig 3 the distribution of KPI values, in this example, the success rate for random access in the cell, for the most

similar cells is shown. The first column shows those cells sharing the existing configuration parameter setting on the target cell. The second column shows the distribution of KPI values for the most similar cells with the suggested new configuration parameter value. The third column shows the KPI value for the target cell for which the reconfiguration action is being considered.

Fig 3 - Expected KPI degradation based on configuration parameter change.

As can be seen, the target cell has a KPI value near the upper end of the range of values for similar cells with the existing PDCCH maximum block error rate configuration parameter setting. The target cell KPI value is outside the range of values for similar cells with the proposed new configuration parameter values. For this reason, the conflict detection mechanism will predict that making this change to the configuration parameter setting will result in degradation to the Random-Access Success Rate KPI and will notify the rApp proposing the change of this prediction.

Fig 4 shows an example where the proposed configuration parameter change is not expected to cause KPI degradation to the target cell.

Fig 4 - No expected KPI degradation based on configuration parameter change.

B. Tabular Representation of Conflict Detection Component Outputs

The conflict detection component identified a list of expected KPI degradations from a proposed configuration parameter change as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 - Predicted KPI Degradations

KPI Category	KPI Name	Target Cell KPI	Avg KPI (existing)	Avg KPI (new)	Predicted KPI Change (%)
Accessibility	Random Access Success Rate	0.739094	0.799743	0.807951	9.31
Integrity	Average Downlink UE Latency	6.837717	8.822479	7.828764	14.49
Availability	Cell Availability	0.999815	0.947938	0.997831	-0.19
Accessibility	Random Access MSG1 Success Rate	0.998494	0.991676	0.990013	-0.84
Retainability	E-RAB Retainability	0.00059	0.003303	0.002902	392.30

The row where a large KPI degradation is predicted is highlighted in red and the rows with small KPI degradations are highlighted in yellow. When a significant predicted degradation in a KPI is identified the rApp that proposed the configuration change will be notified. To safeguard the service levels in the network the proposing rApp can cancel the execution of the proposed change. In some cases, an rApp may execute the proposed configuration parameter change despite notification of predicted KPI degradation.

The results where KPI degradation is predicted are reported back to the rApp that proposed the configuration parameter change so that the decision can be re-assessed with the knowledge of the predicted KPI degradation. The outputs from the conflict detection component are intended to safeguard KPIs in a running network against configuration parameter changes that could result in a reduction in performance of aspects of the network.

The importance of the predicted KPI degradation is not assessed by the conflict detection mechanism. Many performance metrics (such as call completion rate versus call quality) can be a trade-off against each other. The rApp proposing the configuration change can decide if the predicted degradation is acceptable based on factors such as current KPI levels and network goals.

It would also be possible to use the conflict detection component during development of an rApp to test the rApp's algorithm. Developing the algorithms for autonomous components in such a way that they minimize their effects on aspects of network performance other than the aspects which they are designed to optimize is an important way of extending the concept of pre-emptive conflict detection to encompass design-time improvements as well as a run-time solution.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

A. Conclusions

The predictions of KPI degradation produced by the conflict detection component proposed here can be a valuable input to both autonomic and human decision-making processes about applying a specific configuration change. Many aspects of telecommunication networks involve a trade-off between competing KPIs, for example extending the coverage area of a cell will improve handover

metrics but increase average latency in the cell. Pre-emptively detecting conflicts between the reconfiguration actions of multiple rApps can help avoid these actions causing network degradation. To fully realize the network optimization potential of multiple rApps working together additional factors that need to be considered, such as the consideration of specific performance goals for each area of the network.

B. Future Work

The volume of configuration changes that are made in modern telecommunication networks can, however, be so large that it is impractical to guard against any degradation to KPIs. The output from the conflict detection component would be of greater value to a network operator if it could be combined with an intent-based system that was aware of the operator's current priorities and intentions for the network.

An example of this would be on an occasion that an operator knows of an event that will cause traffic to move from one location to another they would intentionally make changes to reduce capacity in a particular area.

In the case of a starting state with non-optimal configurations in cells with similar operating environments, the conflict detection mechanism will not prevent reconfigurations towards a more optimally performing state. An important addition to the mechanism would be a measurement of the confidence associated with each KPI degradation prediction based on factors such as the relative similarity of the comparative examples for each prediction.

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REFERENCES

[1] O-RAN SMO - Service Management and Orchestration, O-RAN
 [2] O-RAN Alliance White Paper, O-RAN: Towards an Open and Smart RAN, October 2018, [online]
 [3] B. Brik, K. Boutiba and A. Ksentini, "Deep Learning for B5G Open Radio Access Network: Evolution, Survey, Case Studies, and Challenges," in IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society, vol. 3, pp. 228-250, 2022, doi: 10.1109/OJCOMS.2022.3146618.
 [4] W. -C. Yang, "Interoperability Testing Tool for Operations and Maintenance Interfaces of 5G Open RAN Base Station," 2022 23rd Asia-Pacific Network Operations and Management Symposium

(APNOMS), Takamatsu, Japan, 2022, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.23919/APNOMS56106.2022.9919897.
 [5] M. Polese, L. Bonati, S. D'Oro, S. Basagni and T. Melodia, "Understanding O-RAN: Architecture, Interfaces, Algorithms, Security, and Research Challenges," in IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 1376-1411, Secondquarter 2023, doi: 10.1109/COMST.2023.3239220.
 [6] L. Bonati, S. D'Oro, M. Polese, S. Basagni and T. Melodia, "Intelligence and Learning in O-RAN for Data-Driven NextG Cellular Networks," in IEEE Communications Magazine, vol. 59, no. 10, pp. 21-27, October 2021, doi: 10.1109/MCOM.101.2001120.
 [7] O-RAN Near-RT RIC Architecture 4.0, O-RAN.WG3.RICARCH-R003-v04.00 published March 2023
 [8] C. Adamczyk and A. Kliks, "Conflict Mitigation Framework and Conflict Detection in O-RAN Near-RT RIC," in IEEE Communications Magazine, May 2023, doi: 10.1109/MCOM.018.2200752.
 [9] H. Zhang, H. Zhou and M. Erol-Kantarci, "Team Learning-Based Resource Allocation for Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN)," ICC 2022 - IEEE International Conference on Communications, Seoul, Korea, Republic of, 2022, pp. 4938-4943, doi: 10.1109/ICC45855.2022.9838763.
 [10] Y. Shu, T. Gao, Z. Zhang and J. Zhang, "A General KPI Anomaly Detection Using Attention Models," 2022 IEEE International Conference on Services Computing (SCC), Barcelona, Spain, 2022, pp. 114-119, doi: 10.1109/SCC55611.2022.00027.
 [11] ETSI, Universal Mobile Telecommunications System (UMTS); LTE; Telecommunication management; Key Performance Indicators (KPI) for Evolved Universal Terrestrial Radio Access Network (E-UTRAN): Definitions (3GPP TS 32.450 version 9.3.0 Release 9), 2022
 [12] Coverage availability and performance aspects for 5G NR, July 2022
 [13] Rui Xu and D. Wunsch, "Survey of clustering algorithms," in IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 645-678, May 2005, doi: 10.1109/TNN.2005.845141.
 [14] V. K. Anand, S. K. A. Rahiman, E. Ben George and A. S. Huda, "Recursive clustering technique for students' performance evaluation in programming courses," 2018 Majan International Conference (MIC), Muscat, Oman, 2018, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/MINTC.2018.8363153.
 [15] Q. Zhang, T. Xu and D. Pi, "A Similarity Measurement Algorithm for Spacecraft Telemetry Time Series," 2022 International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Computer Information Technology (AICIT), Yichang, China, 2022, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/AICIT55386.2022.9930173.
 [16] M. Zhang, "Research on Similarity Search Technique of Variable Long Time Series Data Mining," 2021 5th Annual International Conference on Data Science and Business Analytics (ICDSBA), Changsha, China, 2021, pp. 17-22, doi: 10.1109/ICDSBA53075.2021.00014.
 [17] P. A. Jaskowiak, R. J. G. B. Campello and I. G. Costa, "Proximity Measures for Clustering Gene Expression Microarray Data: A Validation Methodology and a Comparative Analysis", IEEE/ACM Transactions on Computational Biology and Bioinformatics, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 845-857, July-Aug. 2013.
 [18] J. Armstrong, S. Fallon and E. Fallon, "Exploiting Cell Similarities in a Radio Access Network to Enhance Explainability for Autonomic Network Management Systems," 2023 12th International Conference on Control, Automation and Information Sciences (ICCAIS), Hanoi, Vietnam, 2023, pp. 775-780, doi: 10.1109/ICCAIS59597.2023.10382371.
 [19] BeGREEN: SNS-JU 2022 Phase 1 Project